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“DO YOU THINK I HAVE FORGOTTEN?”

They say forgive and forget. And every time you remember, forgive and forget again. Forget everything that hurts. Forgive everyone who is bad. Forget what makes you sad. But it makes me wonder, do you honestly think someone could forget that easy? Because for me, some memories etch themselves deep, even after you've frustratedly tried to close them. Some memories make you happy for a short while and some memories hurt you forever. And when the pain refuses to fade, when it keeps finding its way back into your thoughts no matter how hard you try to let go, how do you learn to live with the latter?

There are moments when I question why I can't move on when I have already accepted everything that happened. I question why, when I have been so forgiving all my life, and why should this be any different.

I wonder why, when I have been so good, it feels like the world is always against me. It seems as if heaven is not on my side that challenges keep finding me, even when I mean well. 'Ah! Maybe this happened because it is meant to be,' or even "Maybe I need to experience this because I still have a lot of things to learn". I feel like I've grown so used to these lines that I didn't notice the depth of suffering I have endured. Not until this year.

I met the saddest, angriest, and most frustrated version of myself. I never thought something could break me so much that, in a snap, I would feel completely different. The hit was so hard, it led me to my room, on my knees, hand over my heart, begging God to ease my pain. I have never been this lost that I don't know where to begin to find the path that could console my brokenness. There are moments when I feel as if the world is moving without me, even after doing so many new things I thought would make me feel okay. But everyone else seems to be running ahead. Chasing dreams. Ticking boxes. Glowing with certainty. Then, I am still here, unable to forget even a single detail, wondering if I missed a sign somewhere, or took a wrong turn. I wish others could feel it from my point of view and they would know this pain, it feels endless.

I often heard that the most dangerous anger is born from a good heart. They endure in silence, remain calm, and forgive endlessly. Until one day, their spirit can no longer bear the weight. I used to think they were just exaggerating it. Should I be happy that I could finally relate to them? That after all this time, I keep bringing the same old stuff over again, it sticks with me every day. How it feels to swallow my past traumas whenever I see something that could potentially trigger them. The shaky hands, the random realization that I am not yet over it. I was just distracted, and once in a while the flashbacks keep coming back.

I know I owe myself an apology for allowing this feeling to consume me. Don't get me wrong, I've tried, really tried, to make peace with this pain. But I just can't explain where it comes from, why no matter how much I try to reconcile with it, it doesn't let me go.

People tell me time heals. That someday, this pain will fade. The year is ending, yet it doesn't feel that way. It feels like I am trapped in a cycle of anger, sadness, and frustration, like I am standing in the ruins of who I used to be, unsure of how to rebuild without losing more pieces of myself along the way.

Indeed, kindness, when poured into the wrong hands, will leave you empty. Not everyone who receives your love intends to honor it. And after giving so much of myself to people who never truly valued it, I've learned that compassion can sometimes be exhausting. For enduring this much, now I feel unimpressed when people call me "strong". Because being strong was not my choice. For me it was survival. I didn't grow into strength. I was forced into it. When I needed help, I had to figure it out alone. When I was hurting, I had to smile anyway. When I feel like crying, I had to hide it. So, when people praise my strength, it doesn't feel like a compliment. It feels like they're applauding the pain I had to swallow.

I resent everything that happened, and resentment is strange because while I genuinely want to forgive wholeheartedly, my mind still struggles to comprehend what I've done wrong to deserve this pain. It's confusing, really, how love and bitterness can coexist. Because yes, I still love you—I do—and I would do anything to mend this relationship. But when it's late at night, it's all I can think about, and it's **draining**. It's the kind of ache that doesn't fade, the kind that keeps replaying the same question over and over: *Why me?* And even when morning comes, I wear a smile, pretending I'm fine, while deep down, I'm still fighting the urge to break. Sure, it didn't kill me, but it scarred me deeply. It left me with unbearable anxiety, fractured trust, and the kind of sadness that lingers even in moments of peace.

I feel like there is no way for me to heal. I think this sadness will never leave me. No matter how much I try, it lingers, buried deep like it was meant to stay. I don't think I'll be free from it. I think I will just stuck in the same pain, carrying the same weight, till the end of my life.

Truth hurts, I know, but there is no denying that this year, this pain, has changed me. I carry it in quiet moments, in deep breaths, in the way I turn away from kindness. And with everything I hold inside, do you really think I have forgotten?

